

Decentring the Study of Migrant
Returns and Return Policies

Key Insights on Nigeria–EU Migration Cooperation: Sovereignty, Challenges, and Pathways for Sustainable Partnership

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Key Insights on Nigeria–EU Migration Cooperation: Sovereignty, Challenges, and Pathways for Sustainable Partnership

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1. Executive Summary

This research digest examines the evolving dynamics of Nigeria’s bilateral cooperation with European Union (EU) Member States in the field of migration diplomacy, focusing particularly on return migration policies. Against the backdrop of increasing irregular migration from Nigeria to Europe, this digest explores the complex interplay of political, economic, and security factors shaping Nigeria’s role as both a country of origin and transit and a key partner in EU migration governance.

Nigeria remains one of the largest source and transit countries for migrants attempting irregular journeys to Europe, prompting intensified efforts by the EU to engage Nigeria through diplomatic channels, development cooperation, and migration management initiatives. In practice, however, these areas are not weighted equally. Migration control, particularly return and readmission, tends to dominate the agenda, while development cooperation and legal migration pathways are often framed as complementary but receive less sustained investment. Bilateral agreements and memoranda of understanding (MoUs) between Nigeria and individual EU states—such as Germany, Italy, and Austria—reflect this pragmatic but imbalance approach. They prioritise border management and return facilitation while offering reintegration support and limited mobility opportunities as incentives rather than central pillars.

The digest highlights Nigeria’s cautious yet strategic posture, emphasising the country’s insistence on sovereignty, developmental benefits, and political legitimacy within migration negotiations. Challenges persist, including political sensitivities around migration control, governance issues such as corruption, and human rights concerns related to returnees. Nigeria’s internal socio-political dynamics, including diaspora politics and regional disparities, further complicate the cooperation landscape.

Key findings underscore the importance of flexible, informal cooperation frameworks that complement formal agreements, allowing for adaptive responses to fluctuating migration flows. The role of financial and development incentives emerges as critical in motivating Nigerian engagement. Moreover, reintegration support mechanisms are pivotal for sustainable return, requiring coordination across multiple sectors and actors at all level of governance.

The digest concludes that effective migration diplomacy with Nigeria hinges on acknowledging the country’s agency and priorities, integrating development goals with migration management, and fostering transparent, trust-based partnerships. Future policy efforts should enhance dialogue on legal migration routes, improve protection standards for returnees in all Nigeria’s regions and at all governance levels, and address governance challenges to strengthen the overall effectiveness of bilateral cooperation.

This digest contributes to a nuanced understanding of Nigeria’s position within EU migration diplomacy, offering policymakers and stakeholders insights to craft more balanced, ethical, and mutually beneficial migration policies.

a. Objective

This research digest investigates the complex factors shaping Nigeria's varying levels of cooperation with individual European Union (EU) Member States regarding return and readmission diplomacy. Despite ongoing and sustained pressure from the EU to conclude a formal, EU-wide readmission agreement, Nigeria has consistently declined such an arrangement. Instead, it has opted to engage selectively through bilateral agreements and memoranda of understanding (MOUs) with specific Member States (Irabor, 2023; Zanker & Jegen, 2019) including Germany, Italy, and Austria. Notably, Nigeria has also maintained relatively smooth return diplomacy with Switzerland, a Schengen Area state, underscoring its pragmatic approach to negotiating return and readmission frameworks across Europe.

This digest seeks to unpack the underlying reasons for Nigeria's differentiated approach by analysing the interplay of domestic political considerations, historical diplomatic relationships, migration flow patterns, and incentives offered by different EU countries. By exploring these dimensions, it aims to provide a nuanced understanding of Nigeria's strategic decisions in return diplomacy and highlight the implications for future EU–Nigeria migration cooperation (Bisong, 2021).

b. Key Findings

- Nigeria is a major African origin and transit country for migrants to the EU, with over 261,000 nationals mainly in Italy, Germany, and Spain. In Germany, close to 14,000 Nigerian asylum seekers are under obligation to leave, yet about 12,500 remain, largely because they lack valid identity documents (DW, 2023). In 2020, the German government reported that about 12,000 Nigerians had their asylum claims rejected and were under return orders, while across the EU an estimated 100,000 Nigerians were living without legal status (Tella, 2020). In 2017, 246 Nigerians were removed from Italy (Bagnoli & Civillini, 2017), 23 from Spain as well as 84 from Switzerland, Germany, Iceland, Austria, Belgium, Hungary, Sweden, and Luxembourg (Ihuamadenyi, 2017). In fact, between 2017 and 2020, after the launch of “voluntary return” programme, around 8,400 Nigerians were deported from Europe (Zandonini, 2020), and many more after then.
- Nigeria's strategic location and population give it strong influence in regional and EU migration policy.
- Migration from Nigeria to the EU occurs through regular (work, study, family) and irregular (smuggling) channels, mainly via the Central Mediterranean (Libya–Italy) and Western Mediterranean (Mali–Morocco–Spain). Drivers include economic hardship, insecurity, environmental issues, and diasporic aspirations.
- Nigeria resists formal EU readmission agreements due to sovereignty, reintegration concerns, and political backlash, preferring bilateral MoUs that allow tailored cooperation and maintain its leverage.
- Flexible, informal cooperation frameworks complement formal agreements, allowing adaptive and pragmatic responses to changing migration flows.
- Financial and development incentives play a crucial role in motivating Nigeria's participation in migration diplomacy.
- Return migration is a key focus of EU–Nigeria cooperation, with most returnees arriving via Lagos, Abuja, and Kano airports from African countries like Libya and Niger—many of whom were stranded migrants enroute Europe.
- Bilateral cooperation varies, from formal, problematic agreements (Austria, Belgium and Ireland) to informal, trust-based models (Germany and Switzerland).
 - ❖ Without a formal treaty, Germany and Switzerland pursue a holistic approach linking migration, development, and reintegration, including vocational training and psychosocial support, maintained by continuous dialogue and high-level political engagement.

- Cooperation depends on incentives (financial aid, security, legal pathways), Nigeria's domestic politics (public resistance, diaspora influence), historical ties (trade, colonial legacies), economic asymmetries, and migration pressure in receiving countries.
- Addressing governance challenges is essential to improve the effectiveness and ethical grounding of bilateral migration cooperation.
- Many legal migration pathways are narrow in scope, underfunded, or hampered by restrictive eligibility criteria. Enhancing legal migration channels is a necessary policy development area.
- Returnees face harsh conditions and human right violations pre and during returns, and protection standards at this stage are important areas for future policy development.
- Reintegration support for returnees is critical for sustainable migration management and requires multisectoral and multi-level coordination. Return and reintegration efforts are uneven and overly centralised in urban hubs, which limits effective reintegration.

C. Relevance

Understanding the variation in Nigeria's cooperation on return and readmission is essential for crafting effective, realistic, and mutually beneficial migration policies between the EU and Nigeria. This variation highlights the need for tailored diplomatic strategies that consider Nigeria's unique political, economic, and social contexts, rather than relying on a uniform, EU-wide approach (Strange & Oliveira Martins, 2019).

Recognising these nuances helps policymakers address the complexities of migration management more pragmatically and fosters more sustainable cooperation on return migration. Moreover, it underscores the broader lesson that migration diplomacy must adapt to the diverse interests and constraints of partner countries to achieve meaningful outcomes (IOM, 2024).

2. Background & Context

2a. Nigeria's Role in EU Migration Diplomacy

i. Overview of Nigeria's Migration Patterns to the EU

Nigeria is a key country of origin for both regular and irregular migration to the EU, making it a priority partner in EU migration governance (European Commission, 2016). As of 2024, 261,345 Nigerian nationals hold valid residence permits across EU Member States. Italy hosts the largest share (105,814 or 40%), followed by Germany (54,699), Spain (31,379), France (20,607), and Ireland (10,214) (European Commission et al., 2024). In addition to these documented populations, a significant number of Nigerians live in irregular status across several EU countries.

Nigerian migration to Europe occurs through both regular and irregular pathways. Legal routes include work, study, and family reunification. However, restrictive visa regimes and the lack of viable legal alternatives have led many to pursue irregular migration. Two major irregular routes are commonly used: the Central Mediterranean route via Niger and Libya to Italy, and the Western Mediterranean route through Mali and Morocco to Spain, including via Ceuta, Melilla, more rarely, the Atlantic Route to the Canary Islands (Uzomah, 2024).

Multiple drivers underpin these migration patterns, and share to shape migration diplomacy processes (Tsourapas, 2021) as well as return (Sahin-Mencutek et al., 2025). Economic challenges—especially youth unemployment and poverty—intersect with insecurity from armed conflict, political instability, and environmental degradation, including the impacts of climate change, are common drivers (Madondo & Dhobha, 2025). Migration is also aspirational: many young Nigerians view it as a path to social mobility and success, influenced

by diasporic role models and transnational networks (Inegbedion, 2022; Carling & Collins, 2017; Lacroix, 2014). Remittances from Nigerians abroad significantly bolster household incomes and national development, reinforcing migration as a rational livelihood strategy (Wapmuk et al., 2014).

Nevertheless, irregular migration carries significant risks. Migrants frequently face exploitation by smugglers, arbitrary detention, and human trafficking—particularly affecting women and girls who are vulnerable to sexual violence (Obi et al., 2019). Nigeria also serves as a transit country for migrants from other West and Central African nations attempting to reach the EU. Those who arrive in Europe often confront legal precarity, discrimination, and threats of deportation, further complicating migration governance and return policy implementation.

In this context, Nigeria plays a strategic dual role in EU migration diplomacy—as both a country of origin and transit and thus a partner in return and readmission efforts (Castillijo, 2017). Its cooperation is shaped by domestic political realities as well as international pressures and incentives, positioning it as a central actor in the design of sustainable, rights-based EU–Africa migration partnerships.

Return migration has become a central pillar of EU–Nigeria migration cooperation since 2016 when the EU-IOM Joint Initiative was launched to address the protection needs and facilitate the return and reintegration of stranded Nigerian migrants in transit countries, and by early 2017 had committed to reintegrate over 3800 Nigerian returnees under EU Trust Fund (EUTF) (IOM, 2022). While a portion of the returnees come from EU Member States, the majority are returned from African countries, particularly Libya, Niger, and Sudan (European Commission et al., 2024). This highlights the predominance of intra-African return flows and reinforces the need for reintegration support irrespective of the return country. Most of these returnees arrive through Nigeria’s main international airports—Lagos, Abuja, and Kano. Notably, many of those returning from Libya and Niger were en route to Europe but either voluntarily returned or were coerced or assisted to do so after becoming stranded (IOM, 2023).

ii. Nigeria’s Strategic Position as a Migration Hub

Nigeria holds a pivotal geographic, demographic, and political position within West Africa, making it a major source country and a critical hub for both intra-regional and extra-regional migration (Ochogwu & Babatunde, 2023). Its vast population, economic size, and leadership in the Economic Community of West African States (ECOWAS) underpin its central role in regional and global migration governance (ECOWAS, 1979).

Nigeria borders Benin, Niger, Chad, and Cameroon, and lies along key migration routes to North Africa and Europe (Edet & Chinazaekpere, 2020). Cities like Kano, Maiduguri, and Agadez (Niger) are part of the Central Mediterranean corridor to Libya and Italy while Lagos and Benin City are major departure points integrated into smuggling and trafficking networks facilitating irregular travel to Europe (Iraboh, 2023).

Nigeria functions as a transit country for migrants from West and Central Africa. Migration flows often begin as circular or regional moves but become internationalised when migrants head toward North Africa and Europe. Porous borders, weak governance, and corruption facilitate informal migration ecosystems involving smugglers and traffickers (Iraboh, 2023).

As Africa’s largest economy, Nigeria attracts migrants from neighbouring ECOWAS countries seeking work, particularly in Lagos and urban centres (Uzomah et al, 2019; Uzomah & Madu, 2020). Simultaneously, high unemployment and inequalities drive outward migration to North Africa and Europe. This dual role amplifies Nigeria’s importance in regional, trans-Mediterranean and international migration.

iii. Nigeria's Diplomatic Weight and Regional Power Role

Nigeria's political influence and population size make its cooperation vital for EU migration governance. Participation in forums like the Valletta Summit (2015) and the EU–Africa Migration Partnership Framework demonstrates Nigeria's growing leverage (Olakpe, 2020). The country currently holds the chairmanship of the Rabat Process for 2025–2026, potentially offering a site of subaltern agency within the African-EU migration dialogue to reframe, slow down, reframe or dilute EU pressure for a formal readmission agreement, favouring bilateral deals with tailored terms. Also, the country plays a leadership role in ECOWAS, whose 1979 Protocol on Free Movement of Persons facilitates visa-free mobility within the region (ECOWAS, 1979). This regional legal mobility often precedes longer journeys toward North Africa and Europe (Brachet, 2018). The EU acknowledges this pattern and engages Nigeria as a strategic interlocutor in African migration management.

iv. Implications for EU Return Diplomacy

Nigeria's complex migration role—origin and transit—significantly shapes EU migration initiatives. Whether through Assisted Voluntary Return and Reintegration (AVRR) programmes, bilateral return arrangements, or managing trafficking routes, Nigeria is essential to EU strategies, and cannot be neglected. The EU has increasingly adopted differentiated bilateral engagement approaches rather than a one-size-fits-all EU-wide model, reflecting Nigeria's strategic position and policy preferences.

2b. The EU's Return Diplomacy with Nigeria

i. Resistance to an EU-wide Readmission Agreement

Despite long-standing efforts by the EU to formalise migration governance frameworks with third countries, Nigeria has consistently resisted entering into a formal EU-wide readmission agreement. This resistance reflects a confluence of political, legal, economic, and diplomatic considerations that reveal the strategic agency of Nigeria in international migration diplomacy. Rather than an EU-wide agreement, Nigeria prefers bilateral arrangements with individual Member States, allowing greater negotiation flexibility and tailored frameworks. Examples include MoUs with Italy (2017), Belgium (2015), and Austria (2012).

Nigeria's bilateral approach reflects a strategic posture to maintain agency in migration diplomacy. Nigeria-Ireland's 2001 bilateral understanding promotes returns, with lack of formal ratification and limited legal enforceability (Oireachtas, 2024). The Nigeria–Austria agreement (2012) formalised procedures but faces operational challenges. Nigeria–Belgium's 2015 MoU supports voluntary and forced returns but struggles with coordination. Nigeria–Italy's 2017 MoU addresses returns amid the Central Mediterranean migration crisis, with limited reintegration depth. Germany's high-engagement, no formal agreement approach emphasises reintegration and development cooperation. Other Member States such as France, the Netherlands, Spain, Denmark, Sweden, Lithuania, and Greece engage Nigeria through various informal or emerging channels (Adhikari et al, 2021; Carrera & Geddes, 2021).

At the core of Nigeria's resistance lies a strong concern for national sovereignty. Interviews during fieldwork reveal that readmission agreements are seen not merely as technical arrangements but as politically charged instruments implicating the country's autonomy over its borders and population. Nigerian authorities perceive such agreements as external impositions that could undermine control over verification procedures. In the context of fragile state–citizen relationships, cooperating too openly risks eroding domestic legitimacy which can jeopardise the stability of the government.

Domestic Backlash and Inadequate Reintegration Support

Nigeria's 2015 migration policy, currently under review, lacks a cohesive national strategy, leaving return cooperation vulnerable to fragmentation and political contestation. Concerns about being perceived as "Europe's border guard" and reports of abuse against Nigerian migrants abroad as well as abusive deportations amplify domestic opposition.

Additionally, inadequate and uneven reintegration support continues to shape Nigeria's reluctance toward formal agreements (European Commission, 2024). In some regions, reintegration support is minimal or entirely absent. Many returnees report fragmented or poorly coordinated assistance upon arrival. Short-term reintegration initiatives and weak accountability mechanisms further contribute to a credibility gap in EU programmes.

Low Profile of the EU

The EU maintains a low profile in Nigeria, as its migration programmes are largely implemented through intermediaries like international organisations and partners (Uzomah et al., 2025). These actors often operate with limited oversight and are constrained by heavy bureaucracy, reducing the effectiveness of interventions. The lack of direct EU engagement weakens accountability and transparency, contributing to Nigeria's hesitation to enter into formal migration agreements.

ii. Bilateral Approaches

2c. Germany–Nigeria Cooperation as a Case Study

Germany represents a unique and illustrative example of deep and sustained engagement with Nigeria on migration and return issues despite the absence of a formal readmission agreement. Unlike other EU Member States that rely on legally binding treaties or memoranda, Germany's approach centres on flexible, trust-based diplomacy, technical cooperation, and comprehensive reintegration support (BAMF & DGAP, 2023).

Since the early 2010s, Germany has prioritised a multifaceted migration partnership with Nigeria, integrating return and reintegration into broader development and security cooperation frameworks. Key elements of this cooperation include:

- **Migration Dialogue and Policy Coordination:** Germany maintains ongoing bilateral dialogues with Nigerian authorities at various levels, fostering information exchange, joint planning, and alignment of migration management strategies. This includes capacity building for Nigerian border management and identity verification systems such as Advanced Passenger Information System (APIS), Biometric E-Gates, Migration Information and Data Analysis System (MIDAS), Border Management Information System (BMIS), and Command and Control Centre in an effort to modernise Nigeria's border management and to ensure smoother return processes.
- **Reintegration Support:** Germany funds programmes aimed at facilitating sustainable reintegration of returnees into Nigerian society. These initiatives include vocational training, entrepreneurship support, and psychosocial counselling, often implemented through partnerships with Nigerian agencies and international organisations like the IOM and German Agency for International Cooperation (GIZ).
- **Collaboration:** Germany works closely with Nigerian authorities through multi-actor partnerships involving federal ministries, GIZ, IOM, and local NGOs (Uzomah, 2025). Central to this is the *Returning to New Opportunities* programme, which offers tailored reintegration support, including job placement, vocational training, micro-grants, and psychosocial services, delivered through joint reintegration centres in Lagos, Benin City, and Abuja. These centres serve as operational hubs for return and reintegration efforts. Germany also provides technical assistance to strengthen Nigeria's capacity for identity verification and returnee management, reinforcing the efficiency and credibility of return procedures.

- **High-Level Political Engagement:** The 2023 visit by German Chancellor Olaf Scholz, followed by the 2024 visit of Germany's Federal Minister for Economic Cooperation and Development, Svenja Schulze, to Nigeria marked high-level political engagements that reinforced Germany's commitment to migration cooperation. Together, these visits opened space for exploring new modalities of partnership, signalled a shift towards more pragmatic and results-oriented engagement, and aimed to deepen developmental and technical collaboration while improving the efficiency of return operations.
- Germany's model demonstrates that meaningful outcomes in migration diplomacy can be achieved without formal treaties, relying instead on mutual trust, continuous dialogue, and responsive programming. This approach allows flexibility to adapt to changing migration dynamics and domestic political contexts in both countries. Furthermore, Germany's strategy highlights the importance of coupling return policies with robust reintegration frameworks to address the root causes of irregular migration and reduce repeat migratory flows.

Overall, the Germany–Nigeria partnership offers valuable lessons for the EU and its Member States on alternative pathways to cooperation that attempts to respect sovereignty concerns while promoting shared interests in orderly return and sustainable reintegration.

3. Explaining the Variation in Nigeria's Cooperation with EU Member States

Nigeria's engagement with the EU on migration management, particularly in return and readmission cooperation, shows significant variation across individual Member States. While the EU promotes a unified migration agenda, bilateral arrangements between Nigeria and specific Member States reflect differentiated approaches, shaped by a combination of political, economic, and diplomatic factors that influence Nigeria's willingness and capacity to cooperate on the return of irregular migrants, with minimal rights violations.

3i. Incentives Offered by Member States

A key factor explaining Nigeria's differentiated cooperation is the type and extent of incentives offered by individual EU Member States. These incentives: financial, developmental, diplomatic, legal, and security-related, serve as leverage to encourage Nigeria's active participation in return agreements or rather arrangements, often aligning migration objectives with broader development and foreign policy goals.

Financial and Development Incentives: Many Member States, including Germany and the Netherlands, have provided financial support for return and reintegration programmes, often through the EU Emergency Trust Fund for Africa (EUTF) and currently Neighbourhood, Development and International Cooperation Instrument (NDICI) or bilateral development cooperation frameworks (Schacht, 2022; European Commission, 2024; Castillejo, 2017). These resources are channelled into skills training, cash grants, or business start-up kits for returnees. Development-oriented projects, such as infrastructure support and youth employment schemes, have also been used to incentivise cooperation, especially in regions and states which are sensitive to migration matters.

Diplomatic and Political Engagement: Some countries have intensified diplomatic relations with Nigeria to facilitate migration dialogue. High-level visits, inter-ministerial working groups, and migration-focused embassies have been instrumental in building trust and sustaining negotiations. Germany, for example, has maintained regular diplomatic contact to ensure policy continuity and demonstrate goodwill beyond migration enforcement.

Security Cooperation: Given Nigeria's persistent security challenges, particularly related to insurgency and terrorism in the Northeast, some Member States have linked migration

cooperation to counter-terrorism assistance and military support. These linkages reflect how migration governance intersects with broader foreign policy and security priorities, allowing for a wider bargaining framework in which return cooperation is embedded in geopolitical strategy.

Legal Migration Pathways: The offer of legal migration opportunities has also emerged as a strategic incentive in return diplomacy. Countries like Germany, Belgium, the Netherlands and Italy have proposed or piloted labour migration schemes, educational and vocational training visas, seasonal worker programmes, and talent partnerships as part of broader mobility frameworks. The latest being the MATCH project for Nigerian and other African youths to work for companies in Belgium, Italy, Luxembourg or the Netherlands (ICMPD, 2022). These legal pathways function in multiple ways for Nigeria:

- They offer a politically palatable justification for return cooperation, mitigating domestic criticism.
- They respond to youth aspirations and labour market pressures, providing alternatives to irregular migration.
- They serve as negotiation capital, with Nigeria demanding more structured and inclusive legal pathways in exchange for more effective collaboration on returns.

While promising in theory, many legal migration offers have been narrow in scope, underfunded, or hampered by restrictive eligibility criteria. This has often undermined their credibility. However, where legal pathways have been implemented meaningfully, especially when tied to reintegration or skills partnerships, they have helped deepen Nigeria's engagement and reduce friction in return operations. An example is the ICT programme with Lithuania which has helped in return collaboration.

Nigeria's cooperation with individual EU Member States is shaped by the type, credibility, and delivery of incentives. Member States that align return diplomacy with tangible economic, legal, and development benefits tend to achieve higher levels of engagement. Those relying on coercive measures or vague promises face limited or inconsistent cooperation.

3ii. Domestic Political Context in Nigeria

Nigeria's domestic political environment plays a crucial role in shaping its approach to return migration cooperation with EU Member States. The interplay of political sensitivities, diaspora dynamics, and governance structures influences how Nigerian authorities negotiate and implement return agreements.

Political Sensitivities and Public Opinion: Return agreements, especially those linked to forced deportations, often provoke significant public and civil society resistance within Nigeria. The return of migrants under coercive circumstances can be perceived domestically as a political failure or a source of social stigma (Uzomah, 2025), making governments wary of being seen as complicit in harsh migration enforcement. Media coverage and activism by human rights organisations tend to highlight the vulnerabilities and challenges faced by returnees, increasing political costs for officials who endorse such deals without adequate reintegration support (Uzomah & Madu, 2025). Consequently, Nigerian policymakers approach return negotiations with caution, often demanding strong assurances about the dignity and sustainability of return processes to avoid domestic backlash.

Diaspora Influence: The Nigerian diaspora exerts considerable influence on return diplomacy. Nigerian communities abroad contribute significantly through remittances, and their political participation, including mobilisation and campaigning from abroad (Oluwasanmi & Fagbadebo, 2025), adds another layer of complexity. Nigerian governments are attentive to the diaspora's views, as negative reactions to return agreements can lead to political pressures

both domestically and internationally (Madubuegwu et al., 2022). Diaspora lobbying groups often advocate for humane treatment of migrants and oppose measures perceived as detrimental to Nigerians abroad. This dynamic incentivises Nigerian authorities to carefully balance cooperation with the EU against the risk of alienating a politically and economically influential constituency.

Regime Type and Governance: Nigeria's status as a democratic republic with active media and civil society means that government actions on migration are subject to public scrutiny and democratic accountability. Election cycles, opposition party positions, and media investigations all influence how openly Nigerian governments engage with return diplomacy. Periods of heightened media attention or political contestation can lead to more cautious or ambivalent stances toward cooperation on returns, especially to migration sensitive states like Edo, Delta and Lagos. Conversely, governments seeking to demonstrate effective migration management or deepen bilateral ties may be more proactive in pursuing agreements.

Governance challenges, such as corruption and weak institutional capacity, also affect the implementation of return policies. Some officials within Nigerian missions, airports and agencies may compromise to provide emergency travel certificate and airport clearance, thereby complicating the translation of diplomatic agreements into effective practice. Many Nigerian migrants lack identification document, and due to lack of a viable database in the country, Nigerian missions are unable to properly identify them (Uzomah et al, 2023).

3iii. Prior Bilateral Relations in the 1990s

Before Italy's 1997 bilateral agreement with Nigeria which included provisions on the return of irregular migrants, the 2001 Germany–Nigeria readmission agreement, and the 2000/2001 Cotonou Agreement (EU–ACP) on readmission, Nigeria's cooperation with EU Member States on return migration was significantly shaped by the history and depth of their existing bilateral relations. These pre-established partnerships in areas such as trade, security, and education often provide a foundation of trust and mutual interest that facilitates more effective migration diplomacy.

Trade, Security, and Education Ties: EU countries with strong economic and security collaborations with Nigeria tend to achieve higher levels of cooperation on return agreements. For example, Germany and Belgium have long-standing bilateral ties that extend beyond migration, including extensive trade relations, joint security initiatives, and educational exchanges. These connections create a framework of ongoing dialogue and institutional linkages, which can be leveraged during return negotiations. Security cooperation, particularly in counter-terrorism and border management, is a crucial factor influencing willingness to engage on return migration. Countries like Germany, France, the Netherlands and Italy, that support Nigeria's efforts in maintaining regional stability often receive more cooperation in migration matters, as these issues are seen as interconnected.

Similarly, educational partnerships and scholarship programmes such as Invest Your Talent in Italy, Netherlands Fellowship Programme (NFP), German Academic Exchange Service (DAAD), Campus France Nigeria, foster goodwill and interpersonal connections that may translate into more collaborative migration management efforts.

Colonial Legacy and Informal Cooperation: Historical and colonial legacies continue to influence Nigeria's migration diplomacy, even if indirectly. For instance, Nigeria's longstanding historical ties with the United Kingdom—although the UK is no longer part of the EU but that has benefited Ireland—shape informal models of cooperation that extend to EU countries with similar colonial histories or legal frameworks. These historical ties often contribute to shared languages, legal systems, and institutional cultures that ease communication and negotiation processes. While not always formalised in treaties, such

informal cooperation networks allow for pragmatic arrangements and flexible dialogue on return migration. In contrast, countries without these historical connections may face greater challenges in building trust and sustained engagement with Nigerian counterparts.

3iv. Economic Asymmetries

Economic disparities between Nigeria and individual EU Member States play a pivotal role in shaping the dynamics of return migration cooperation. The relative wealth and financial influence of EU countries affect their capacity to negotiate and implement return agreements.

Influence of Wealthier States: Countries with larger economies and more substantial aid budgets, such as Germany, Italy, and France, have greater leverage in negotiations with Nigeria. These states can offer significant financial incentives, development assistance, and reintegration support packages that make cooperation more attractive for Nigerian authorities. For example, wealthier Member States often finance infrastructure projects linked to migration management, including training centres for returnees, shelters, and community development programmes. These investments serve dual purposes: they address some of Nigeria's development needs while incentivising Nigerian cooperation in readmission and return operations. Despite its power asymmetries, such economic leverage enables these countries to structure more comprehensive and mutually beneficial agreements, improving their chances of sustained collaboration.

Repatriation Volume and Pressure: Another important factor is the volume of migrants these countries receive and subsequently seek to repatriate. States like Italy and Germany, which experience higher numbers of irregular Nigerian migrants, have a stronger interest in establishing structured and formalised return mechanisms. The sheer scale of returns often compels these countries to intensify diplomatic efforts, allocate greater resources to reintegration, and pursue bilateral agreements tailored to facilitate effective repatriation processes. Conversely, countries with fewer Nigerian migrants like Poland, Luxembourg and Greece tend to have lesser pressing incentives to engage deeply in return negotiations, which can lead to more informal or ad hoc cooperation.

3v. Actual Migration Flows

The volume and nature of migration flows from Nigeria to various EU Member States significantly influence the countries' approaches to return diplomacy and the likelihood of formal cooperation agreements.

Irregular Migration Pressure: Member States that experience higher numbers of irregular migrant arrivals are under greater pressure to remove them including Nigerians as way to manage their borders and migration systems effectively. Countries such as Italy, Spain, and Germany, which serve as key entry points or destinations for Nigerian migrants, are more incentivised to pursue formalised return agreements. This pressure arises from the operational and political challenges posed by irregular migration, including increased border enforcement costs, administrative burdens, and domestic public opinion, all of which demand stronger migration control. To address these challenges, these Member States actively seek negotiated readmission agreements or MOUs with Nigeria to facilitate smoother and more predictable return procedures.

Operational Needs: The capacity of Member States to identify, detain, and process Nigerian migrants directly affects their return diplomacy strategies. Countries like the Netherlands, Denmark, France, Germany and Sweden with robust immigration enforcement infrastructure can push for more structured and formalised cooperation frameworks, as they are better equipped to implement return decisions efficiently. Conversely, Member States with less developed operational capabilities like Poland, Lithuania and Greece may rely on informal or bilateral mechanisms that are less binding but still facilitate some level of cooperation. Additionally, some countries like Germany and the Netherlands prioritise capacity-building

programmes in Nigeria to improve identification and documentation processes, further supporting return operations.

The intensity of irregular migration flows and the operational capacity to manage returns drive the varied nature and depth of Nigeria's cooperation with individual EU Member States in return diplomacy.

4. Key Takeaways & Policy Implications

a. Summary of Findings

i. Factors Explaining Variation in Cooperation

- **Diverse Incentive Packages:** The degree of Nigeria's cooperation varied significantly depending on the nature and extent of incentives offered by individual EU Member States. Financial aid, development assistance, and technical support were key motivators.
- **Political and Diplomatic Relations:** Stronger bilateral political ties and history of diplomatic engagement positively influenced Nigeria's willingness to cooperate.
- **Issue linkages & Security Concerns:** Cooperation was enhanced when linked to broader security cooperation, including efforts to combat trafficking, terrorism and organised crime.
- **Domestic Political Sensitivities in Nigeria:** Internal political dynamics and public opinion shaped Nigeria's responsiveness, with some Member States better navigating these sensitivities through tailored engagement.
- **Flexibility and Informality:** Flexible, informal agreements (arrangements) without heavy bureaucratic demands were often more effective than rigid formal treaties.

ii. Most Effective Strategies to Secure Nigeria's Engagement

- **Combination of Incentives and Dialogue:** Member States combining financial incentives with sustained diplomatic dialogue saw better cooperation outcomes.
- **Integration with Development Programmes:** Aligning migration cooperation with development initiatives that address root causes of migration increased Nigeria's buy-in.
- **Leveraging Security Partnerships:** Linking return agreements with security collaboration enhanced trust and willingness to implement return policies.
- **Respect for Sovereignty:** Approaches that respected Nigeria's sovereignty and political context fostered a more collaborative atmosphere.
- **Incremental and Flexible Agreements:** Step-by-step, adaptable arrangements allowed for adjustments and built mutual confidence over time.

b. Policy Recommendations for the EU and Member States

i. Pursuing Bilateral Approaches Versus Formal Agreements

- **Maintain Bilateral Flexibility:** Given the political complexity and Nigeria's preference for flexible cooperation, the EU should continue emphasising bilateral agreements with Member States rather than pushing for a one-size-fits-all formal treaty.
- **Promote Coordination at EU Level:** While maintaining bilateralism, enhanced EU coordination can prevent overlap and fragmentation which will ensure coherent migration diplomacy.
- **Support Nigeria's Agency:** Policies should acknowledge Nigeria's domestic political context and allow it to steer cooperation processes, strengthening trust and sustainability.
- **Strategically Engage African Institutions:** Explore options for engaging the African Union and its institutions in negotiations on readmission and support programmes.

Nigeria positions itself as a regional superpower and upholds an “Africa-centred” foreign policy. This ideological stance of aspiring to act as a “big brother” in the region may motivate Nigeria to accept more structured agreements, including formal readmission arrangements, if framed as regional leadership opportunities.

ii. Most Effective Incentives for Future Negotiations

- Decentralised Return Strategies: Prioritise routing returnees through airports closer to their home communities (e.g., Benin City, Enugu, Sokoto, Jos, Ilorin, Jalingo, Port Harcourt) instead of central hubs like Lagos, Kano, or Abuja. This can increase sub-national government engagement, encourage governor support for reintegration, reduce bureaucracy, and demonstrate the EU’s commitment to humane, sustainable returns.
- Targeted Development Assistance: Link migration cooperation to development projects focused on unemployment, vocational training, and economic empowerment at the community level to address irregular migration drivers.
- Expansion of Legal Migration Pathways: Increase access to labour mobility schemes, study visas, and circular migration, offering youth dignified alternatives to irregular routes.
- Enhance Institutional and Technical Capacity Support: Deeper strengthening of Nigerian migration and border management through financial and enhanced technical assistance to improve transparency and operational efficiency.
- Capacity Building for Readmission and Reintegration: Train officials and CSOs on the benefits of readmission and reintegration as a tool for individual recovery and national development.
- Security and Anti-Trafficking Collaboration: Support joint EU-Nigeria initiatives for intelligence sharing and transnational crime prevention.
- Support for Local Research and Media Engagement: Fund research and media campaigns to improve policy, visibility, and public narratives around migration and return.
- Ensuring that any fund released for return and reintegration activities should be done with the involvement of stipulated number of local chiefs, town union presidents and community members.
- Respect for Political Sensitivities: Avoid coercive approaches; foster partnerships based on mutual benefit and Nigeria’s sovereignty.

Prioritising decentralised returns alongside developmental, institutional, and legal reforms offers a pragmatic roadmap for EU–Nigeria cooperation, making the process more humane and politically sustainable.

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